

Openalex Concepts Classification:
A Critical Assessment of the Concept of Psychology

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ISI 5302: Knowledge Organization
Fall 2023
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1 Introduction

OpenAlex is an answer to the discontinuation of Microsoft Academic Graph and the need for a replacement. It is an API based software that contains a database of around 250 million documents, categorized within 65,000 different concepts. Created by OurResearch, OpenAlex is a free and open software that specializes in open-source documents. The database revolves around entities and how these entities relate to each other. This creates a web of information that hierarchically organizes information into a free database accessible by anyone. OpenAlex can be used by researchers to create their own search engines, find trends, and manage them, and identify key groups of information, although the latter can be problematic with the questionable conciseness that will be seen later in this report. In this study, we present a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the psychology branch of the classification system. We employed a Python script, utilizing recursive functions to extract and organize quantitative values from the expansive OpenAlex spreadsheet. The key objective is to unravel the distribution and relationships within the psychology tree, shedding light on the hierarchical structure and characteristics of the concept hierarchy. Notably, our analysis identifies 8,531 concepts descending from the level 0 concept of psychology. A unique feature of the OpenAlex classification system is the allowance for concepts to have multiple parent concepts, introducing complexity to the conventional hierarchy. Our quantitative and qualitative analyses, visualized through bar graphs and Sankey diagrams, offer insights into the multiplicity of parents across different hierarchy levels and reveal potential discrepancies and irregularities within the system. The process of assessing the alignment of indexed terms with assigned concepts provides insights into the quality and relevance of the available literature and its database. Correct assignments of concepts can aid in information retrieval- the more the academic discourse within a particular field remains focused, the more it offers a deeper understanding of the content. To evaluate the indexing in OpenAlex, 15 documents were

randomly selected under specific concepts, which were also chosen at random. The aim is to provide an analysis that can shed light on the precision of the indexing in OpenAlex in relation to psychology, and whether users can trust its quality.

2 Literature review

Being a relatively new organizational system, OpenAlex does not have a lot of scholarly articles written on it, and this means researching specifically this software can be a little difficult. That said, there is a good amount of research currently being done, and there have been many good scholarly works written comparing OpenAlex with other long-standing databases. Another beneficial aspect of being a new system is that most of these articles give different respective views on the database and allow for a simply structured analysis of the system.

OpenAlex was created and launched as a replacement for Microsoft Academic Graph, considered at one time to be irreplaceable. OpenAlex operates as a fully open source of scholarly metadata (Priem et al., 2022). The articles that are found through OpenAlex are themselves open source, and this has been a major selling point of the database. The adoption of similar aspects of Microsoft Academic Graph was smooth, as OpenAlex operates in much the same way. There were some differences however, such as in the improvements made to classifications and improvements to document type specifications (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023). Most of the fields of study used to classify documents by Microsoft Academic Graph were continued in OpenAlex, and the remaining 10% were improved upon. In the case of the concept of psychology, 40.64% of the psychology papers on OpenAlex are assigned only to this concept. In Microsoft Academic Graph there were only ~8.1 million assignments under psychology, whereas OpenAlex has ~14 million (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023).

OpenAlex operates as a heterogeneous directed graph with a structure of scholarly entities that have connections between them. All these entities have an individual ID that is

expressed as a URL. These entities are works, authors, venues, institutions and concepts, the latter of which is the focus for this report (Priem et al., 2022). Concepts in OpenAlex are the subjects and ideas that the works are written about. There are roughly 65,000 concepts indexed in OpenAlex, and each has a connection to a Wikidata ID. These concepts are hierarchical and are contained in a concept tree that is an adapted version of the one used by Microsoft Academic Graph. There are six levels of hierarchical classification in OpenAlex, and these branch out in a parent-child tree style system (Etzel, 2023). The assignment of concepts is an automatic process based on the learning classifier employed by Microsoft Academic Graph. The code for this classifier is open source, and 85% of the documents in the database have at least one concept applied to them (Priem et al., 2022). The direct link to a Wikidata concept in relation to the topic of psychology can be made when comparing the number of works in the database and the views on Wikipedia (Arroyo-Machado & Costas, 2023).

Microsoft Academic Graph was the predecessor of OpenAlex and many of the features of Microsoft Academic Graph have been incorporated into OpenAlex. For purposes of brevity, from this point on Microsoft Academic Graph will be expressed using its acronym “MAG”. MAG was not an open-source database and ran based off a subscription system that added data every few weeks. This is similar to how often OpenAlex adds data. MAG included articles in other languages and contained over a billion references (*The Microsoft Academic Knowledge Graph*, n.d.). MAG, and later OpenAlex, contained significantly more bibliographic information than Wikidata, which meant OpenAlex was able to contain and classify a larger collection of articles. In comparison to MAG's fields of study, OpenAlex makes use of concepts. Fields of study in MAG were also a parent-child relationship and were hierarchical (*The Microsoft Academic Knowledge Graph*, n.d.).

With more and more scholarly and scientific articles being published, it is becoming increasingly more difficult to find and cover all the available resources when researching a

project. Researchers are relying on very large databases of data to understand the topics they have chosen to work with (Jiao et al., 2023). This means that as with everything, the databases themselves are evolving to meet the changing needs of researchers. OpenAlex is no exception and has shown a strong potential for future use as a research database. However, it is still new, and not without challenges, which will be spoken about further in this report. Databases such as Web of Science and Scopus have been around for a much longer time and while they contain less documents, they have much smoother systems of classification and organization. One strength that OpenAlex has over other databases is that it contains more conference publications, which is beneficial to academic and medical research, especially in psychology, which often relies heavily on conferences and collaboration to advance scientifically (Jiao et al., 2023). OpenAlex also has the most comprehensive collection of publications, branching across multiple concepts and classifications. Some other databases make use of categories of classification that are not present in OpenAlex, which instead combines them into broader concepts that envelope more works.

OpenAlex does not restrict the metadata that it retrieves, which can be both beneficial as well as detrimental. Using an automated system of classification means that there is still a need for some form of quality assurance. The research of this project as well as others has shown that there is some amount of error in the concepts applied to certain documents as well as in the hierarchical branches. Some children do not line up with their parents or are placed in the wrong order. Older databases tend to have a higher degree of accuracy in their document type classifications and the metadata they contain is often of a higher quality (Jiao et al., 2023). There are also challenges that arise in providing access to those who provided previous research data. Data is also updated regularly and because of this it is difficult to retrieve the same version of the data that was accessed at an earlier point in time. However, despite these challenges, APIs such as OpenAlex can help researchers to gain a deeper insight into research trends. They

also assist in developing a better understanding of a researcher's field and help them to make more informed decisions about their work (Velez-Estevez et al., 2023).

When OpenAlex was created, most of the works contained in MAG were carried over and added to the database of OpenAlex. When this happened, a lot of effort was put into preserving the metadata of the works. This process was successful, with 90% of the documents finding equivalent classification within OpenAlex (Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023). However, 10% of the documents found no home, and so had to be reclassified under new concepts. This process was also marked by the changes made to document type specifications, which meant that some documents from MAG had to be reclassified under new categories of document in OpenAlex. OpenAlex does not aim to necessarily reinvent what MAG began, but rather to improve on that system of organization.

3 Evaluation

3.1 Quantitative Analysis

As mentioned, our analysis of OpenAlex focuses specifically on the psychology branch of the classification system. A Python script was employed to extract quantitative values from the comprehensive OpenAlex spreadsheet, utilizing a recursive function to organize and count concepts while considering the repetition concepts owing to potential multiplicity of parent concepts. This quantitative analysis sheds light on the distribution and relationships within the psychology tree and provides valuable insights into the structure and characteristics of the concept hierarchy.

Psychology is situated at the foundational level (level 0), the analysis identifies a total of 8,531 concepts derived from this root in the hierarchy. The subsequent levels, spanning from level 1 to level 5, generally exhibit a descending trend in the number of concepts. As illustrated

in Figure 1, there are 14 level 1 concepts, 2,801 level 2 concepts, 3,906 level 3 concepts, 1,471 level 4 concepts, and 339 level 5 concepts.

Figure 1: Bar graph depicting the number of concepts as a function of hierarchy. All concepts counted fall under the overarching level 0 concept of psychology.

An interesting characteristic to OpenAlex classification is the allowance for concepts to have multiple parent concepts. This multiplicity introduces complexity into the typical classification system, challenging the conventional hierarchy. Descriptive statistics, as can be seen in Figure 2, highlight the average number of parents across different levels of the hierarchy. At level 1, concepts have an average of 1.27 parents, indicating a relatively straightforward relationship. However, as the hierarchy deepens, the average number of parents increases, reaching 2.24 at level 2, 1.56 at level 3, 1.49 at level 4, and 1.66 at level 5.

Figure 2: Bar graph comparing the average number of parent concepts in levels 1 through 5. All concepts counted fall under the overarching level 0 concept of psychology.

The multiplicity in parents adds a layer of intricacy to the classification system and provides interconnection between various disciplines and fields of research. However, it also raises concerns about the clarity and interpretability of the hierarchy.

3.2 Qualitative Analysis of OpenAlex Concepts: Clinical Psychology

In the examination of the OpenAlex concepts classification system, our specific focus was the Level 1 concept “clinical psychology.” This qualitative analysis aimed to investigate the hierarchical structure and semantic relationships among the 171 concepts nested under “clinical psychology”. A Sankey diagram was crafted using an Excel file, offering a visual representation to discern potential discrepancies and irregularities within the classification system.

The Sankey diagram, shed light on the complex interplay of concepts within “clinical psychology”. Its utility extended beyond the visual representation. The creation of the Sankey required making an excel file where all concepts under “clinical psychology” were placed side by side in order of their class level. This method allowed us to clearly visualize how concepts

were hierarchically arranged, revealing both strengths but mainly flaws in the system's organizational structure.

As we evaluated the concepts, we distinguished between appropriate and inappropriate classifications. An appropriately classified concept would be understandably related to its parent concept and the overarching concept of clinical psychology. In addition, its OpenAlex definition and IDs on the API would be relevant to the concept. Out of the 171 concepts, 119 were deemed appropriate, while 52 were identified as inappropriate. Further investigation of inappropriate concepts unveiled three distinct types of errors, each exemplifying unique challenges within the classification system.

Type 1 Errors: Synonymous Terms

This category highlighted instances where synonymous terms were treated as distinct entities. There were 7 identified synonymous concepts; cases of synonymy all held some similarity in spelling or were derived from the same root. An illustrative example is the trio of concepts: “burnout syndrome”, “occupational burnout”, and “burn out”. Despite sharing exact definitions on OpenAlex, they were inconsistently classified. A similar instance arose with “attention deficit” placed under “attention deficit hyperactivity disorder”, revealing an outdated term that created inconsistencies in semantic relationships. Similarly, “coping (psychology)” and “coping behaviour” held the same OpenAlex concept definition, emphasizing the need for precise semantic relationships and concept singularity.

Type 2 Errors: Misplaced Terms

Type 2 errors were characterized by misplaced terms, presenting challenges in accurate and intuitive hierarchical classification. A notable case was the confusion between “atomoxetine” and “atomoxetine hydrochloride”. Despite referring to the same compound, one concept was flagged as a Type 2 error, emphasizing the need for precision in hierarchical placement. Another convoluted example is the level 2 concept “eating disorders”. Eating

disorders are clinically diagnosed disorders while disordered eating is an abnormal eating behaviour. In this classification, “disordered eating” was found under “eating disorders” when it should be a sister concept. “Binge eating” (a disordered eating behaviour) was found under eating disorders but it should be under disordered eating. The concepts “binge-eating disorder” and “eating disorder inventory” were classified as children of “bulimia nervosa”. In fact, they should be sister concepts to it. This automated bottom-up method of concept classification is faulty, often leading to confusion between concepts that are similar in nature but possess distinct criteria in their respective fields.

Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Anorexia nervosa	
Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Binge eating	
Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Bulimia nervosa	Binge-eating disorder
Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Bulimia nervosa	Eating Disorder Inventory
Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Disordered eating	Female athlete triad
Clinical Psychology	Eating disorders	Eating Attitudes Test	

Figure 3: Screenshot of spreadsheet, demonstrating structure used for analysis and complications in concept classification under level 2 concept "eating disorders". Appropriately classified concepts are in green cells, inappropriately classified concepts are in red cells.

Type 3 Errors: Irrelevant Terms

Type 3 errors highlighted instances where terms, despite sometimes sounding appropriate, held irrelevant definitions in the context of Clinical Psychology. “Delay discounting” and “temporal discounting” were flagged as Type 3 errors due to OpenAlex defining them as “economic valuation definitions”, which were incongruent with the field of psychology. Coincidentally, the term temporal discounting is a concept in clinical psychology and developmental psychology, Reed and Luiselli defines it as “the phenomenon in which the value of a reward decreases as the time delay until its receipt increases” (2011). It seems that OpenAlex assigned both “delay discounting” (which seems to be synonymous to the economic term “hyperbolic discounting”) and “temporal discounting”, the same definition due to similarities in names. One was classified in the wrong field while the other was assigned the wrong definition. Instances like these showcase the challenges in deducing context from terms.

The analysis identified other peculiar fallacies. For instance, the term “female athlete triad”, classified as a Level 4 concept under “disordered eating”, contradicted the typical hierarchical structure, where one would expect to see symptoms (a subdivision of a larger concept) listed under a condition. What led us to believe this concept was erroneously classified were the parent concepts. The disorder is called a triad due to three notable symptoms; amenorrhea, disordered eating, and osteoporosis (Raj et al., 2023). The concept has “amenorrhea” and “disordered eating” as parents but is lacking osteoporosis, which is an existing concept in OpenAlex. We agree that it is best classified under “sport psychology”, which would ideally be changed to a level 1 concept, adjacent to “clinical psychology”. This scenario demonstrates that OpenAlex may readily make links between concepts, but it does not do it in a consistent fashion throughout its web of concepts.

The examination also drew attention to the inclusion of psychology-related concepts under “clinical psychology” that should be considered distinct level 1 concepts. Concepts like “forensic psychology”, “sport psychology”, “counselling psychology”, and others, though related to psychology, seem broad and general, challenging their classification as subcategories of “clinical psychology”.

In certain instances, concepts that seemed like they belonged were placed under “clinical psychology” despite their definitions being unrelated to the field. "Parental monitoring," for example, was defined by OpenAlex as a "software feature allowing content filtering," (OpenAlex API, 2023) demonstrating a lack of contextual relevance. It's plausible that the AI inferred correlation due to the presence of other valid concepts under "clinical psychology" like "parenting style" and "parental skills."

Moreover, seemingly random Level 2 concepts, such as “group effect”, “human female”, “hopefulness”, and “partner effects”, presented challenges in establishing direct connections to clinical psychology.

This was a very interesting class of concepts to study. Clinical psychology is a highly interdisciplinary in the field of psychology and clinical studies. Since many social, genetic, familial, and environmental factors influence an individual’s psychology, a wide array of concepts can be pertinent in a clinical sense. This is emphasized by the observation that many multi-parented concepts classified under “clinical psychology” have parents in different branches of psychology or psychiatry. These identified errors and patterns, ranging from synonymous terms to misplaced and irrelevant concepts, highlight the necessity for ongoing investigation and refinement.

Figure 4: Pie chart illustrating distribution of concept classification error types in concepts nested under “clinical psychology”.

3.3 Evaluation of indexing

The process of evaluating the indexing of concepts is pivotal in assessing the quality and reliability of OpenAlex. For this exercise, 3 concepts were randomly chosen in different levels: Perceptual psychology, psychological trauma, and Asian psychology. From each of

these concepts 15 documents were also randomly extracted to provide an unbiased view of the quality. The process of evaluation was done by two human indexers, assessing the aboutness of the documents in relation to the assigned concept. Figure 5 is a summary of the results.

Figure 5: Results of the concepts and related documents

The titles associated with Perceptual Psychology provide various aspects related to perception and cognition. 9 of the 15 documents are related to the perceptual psychology directly. In Wikidata (2023), perceptual psychology is defined as a “branch of psychology that examines the proportion of subjective perception”, the definition provided by Wikidata is still ambiguous and does not provide a clear explanation as to what perceptual psychology means for users to understand the concept without having to rely on other resources. In Wikipedia (2023), “Perceptual psychology is a subfield of cognitive psychology that concerns the conscious and unconscious innate aspects of the human cognitive system: perception.” (para. 1). Given that Perceptual Psychology is a subfield within Cognitive Psychology, its correct representation within OpenAlex is essential. It is noteworthy that Cognitive Psychology is classified as a level 1 concept with 103 children in level 2. However, it is observed that Perceptual Psychology is not among these level 2 children. Instead, it exists as a child of Differential Psychology, itself categorized under School Psychology. Therefore, it is necessary to integrate Perceptual Psychology within its appropriate hierarchy to ensure an accurate

depiction of the concept. Certain extracted documents, such as "Receiver Psychology Turns 20: Is it Time for a Broader Approach?" or "Cognitive Styles in the Context of Modern Psychology: Toward an Integrated Framework of Cognitive Style," may not explicitly reference perception in their titles. Nevertheless, it is crucial to note that the indexing process considers not only the titles but also the abstracts of these documents, where indexers will find a relationship between cognition and perception. Titles such as "The cognitive revolution: a historical perspective" and "Towards a Revised Cognitive Psychology for New Advances in Learning and Instruction" appear less directly linked to perceptual psychology, and leaning more towards cognitive psychology, potentially weakening the overall coherence of the concept.

Psychological Trauma is a child of Clinical Psychology, Psychiatry, and Psychotherapist. It exists as a level 2 concept with multiple parents and no children. The documents under Psychological Trauma demonstrate a strong correlation with the designated concept, encompassing a wide range of subjects related to it. Noteworthy titles like "Vicarious Traumatization" and "Racism and Psychological and Emotional Injury" shows the diverse nature of discussions on trauma from the selected collection. The 15 documents extracted at random all contain the word "trauma" in either title, abstracts, or both. Therefore, OpenAlex indexing algorithm correctly detects the concept based on clear wording of the subject matter. The third concept is called Asian Psychology. It is a concept with multiple parents and two children (see figure 6) and there is no definition of it in Wikidata.

Figure 6: Asian Psychology and its relationship with related concepts

While Asian Psychology is an unclear concept, for the sake of analysing the documents associated with this context, Asian Psychology is considered as the exploration of psychology within the diverse cultural, social, and historical contexts of Asian societies. Titles such as "A Century of Chinese Developmental Psychology" and "Advancing Positive Psychology in South East Asia" provides perspectives to psychology in the Asian context. From 15 documents only 4 are correctly assigned to the concept since it targets, in some respects, Asian societies.

Figure 7: Co-occurrence analysis of Asian Psychology using VosViewer

Given that the concept revolves around the examination of psychology within a social context, it is more appropriate to categorize documents under Social Psychology. On Wikidata (2023), Social Psychology is characterized as the "scientific study of social effects on people's thoughts, feelings, and behaviours," aligning closely with what Asian Psychology targets. In figure 7, the Co-occurrence analysis conducted using VosViewer produces a term map. In this map, the size of keyword's label corresponds to the frequency of its occurrence, and the proximity of two terms signifies their closeness. The analysis reveals a noticeable association between Social Psychology, Sociology, and Asian Psychology. This connection reinforces the interrelated nature of these fields, highlighting the shared focus on understanding how social factors influence individuals' cognitive processes, emotions, and behaviours within the context of Asian cultures.

Although 15 documents for each concept may not provide an extensive dataset for assessing indexing quality, it does establish a reliable initial foundation for understanding how OpenAlex database have gaps. Since the database is still new, it is necessary to conduct quality assessment reviews to improve the indexing process by collaborating with academic institutions and subject matter experts.

4 Conclusion

OpenAlex as a system of classification has a lot of the right ingredients to become one of the best, but it still has many challenges to overcome. There are large amounts of classifications that do not make sense and do not apply to the documents they are classifying. There is also a hurdle of creating a database that has an easier way to search for documents as the majority of those using it may not have experience using API formats. While it is definitely the largest database, it still has challenges that some of the older databases, such as Web of Science and Scopus, may not face. The intent of being a fully open-source database to allow access to everyone is only as beneficial as the accuracy of the information contained within it.

This means that OpenAlex has a long way to go to develop a better system of organization for the data it contains, especially with the increasing number of documents being published every year. Information, and especially information in digital formats, is increasing. Alongside that, there is a large increase in the push for free access to that information, and this puts OpenAlex in an excellent position to improve itself and establish itself as the premier source of open-source information.

The results of our analysis present a detailed snapshot of the OpenAlex classification system, specifically within the psychology domain. The hierarchical distribution of concepts, as depicted in Figure 1, highlights a descending trend in the number of concepts as hierarchy levels increase, with an intriguing multiplicity of parent concepts. The Sankey diagram, employed for a qualitative analysis of the Level 1 concept "clinical psychology," reveals both strengths and flaws in the system's organizational structure. Notably, our examination of 171 concepts under "clinical psychology" revealed 119 appropriately classified concepts and 52 inappropriate classifications, categorized into three distinct error types. These errors, ranging from synonymous terms to misplaced and irrelevant concepts, underscore the challenges in maintaining precision and consistency within the OpenAlex classification system. The identification of such errors emphasizes the need for ongoing investigation and refinement to enhance the interpretability and accuracy of the hierarchy, especially in interdisciplinary fields like clinical psychology.

The evaluation of the indexing of concepts within OpenAlex, as demonstrated through the analysis of three randomly chosen concepts (Perceptual Psychology, Psychological Trauma, and Asian Psychology), sheds light on both the strengths and weaknesses of the database. The assessment was conducted through the examination of 15 randomly selected documents for each concept by two human indexers, aiming to provide an objective view of the quality of indexing.

The analysis of Perceptual Psychology reveals a significant discrepancy in its representation within OpenAlex. While some of the selected documents do align with the concept, the hierarchical classification places it under Differential Psychology, a categorization that seems inaccurate. On the other hand, the evaluation of Psychological Trauma demonstrates a strong correlation between the concept and the selected documents. The clear and consistent use of the word "trauma" in titles and abstracts enables the OpenAlex indexing algorithm to accurately identify and categorize documents under Psychological Trauma, which made the concept well-represented in the database. Asian Psychology, as a concept, poses challenges in terms of definition and representation. With only four out of 15 documents correctly assigned, there is a notable gap in indexing accuracy. A co-occurrence analysis was done using VosViewer to analyse the interconnected of Social Psychology and Asian Psychology, which provides valuable insight and possibility to categorize documents under Social Psychology instead.

In the broader context, the assessment of these concepts and their associated documents, while based on a limited dataset, serves as an initial foundation for identifying gaps in the OpenAlex database. As the latter is still in its early stages, collaboration with academic institutions and subject matter experts becomes critical for conducting quality assessment reviews. These collaborative efforts will contribute to refining the indexing process, ensuring accuracy, and enhancing the overall reliability of OpenAlex as a valuable resource for information retrieval.

Figure 9: Sankey diagram illustrating classification of descendant concepts of level 1 concept “clinical psychology.”

Data Resources

Link to excel spreadsheet used for qualitative analysis of “clinical psychology”:

https://uottawa-my.sharepoint.com/personal/mmoni071_uottawa_ca/_layouts/15/guestaccess.aspx?share=EeC3CAVFiu9Lj62AdIMTTQ0B9GMNW7-n5qTbw7IOOUuE2Q&e=YrvoJw

Folder containing python scripts used and output: https://uottawa-my.sharepoint.com/personal/mmoni071_uottawa_ca/_layouts/15/guestaccess.aspx?share=EiRi-86hv9hOvgg8RUMbNiwBdDyEdmGmWqgUP7jeYn54Tw&e=pOfrTX

Link to excel spreadsheet used to evaluate the indexing of the 3 concepts: https://uottawa-my.sharepoint.com/personal/aoumy076_uottawa_ca/_layouts/15/guestaccess.aspx?share=EbxCStRSRVtJu2lRo-O76zoBH7T84FVj8F1Q8XjeSRoHjQ&e=xYks3W

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